

Supporting Arctic Communities by Addressing Wildfire and Air Quality Concerns

www.arcticpassion.eu

Effective communication during environmental crises, such as wildfires and air quality emergencies is vital. Providing Indigenous communities and local institutions with accessible, user-friendly tools can increase awareness and resilience as well as help protect their health.

The Arctic region is experiencing more frequent and longer-lasting fires, resulting in increased emissions. Increasing economic activities further add to the air pollution, intensifying the problem.

Monitoring air quality can be difficult; Information is often fragmented or outdated. Dedicated monitoring services like INFRA and AURORAE can save time and effort, and help with protecting Arctic communities' health.

Services like INFRA and AURORAE can provide better access to information on ongoing hazards as well as providing messages tailored to specific needs at local scale.

Stay updated on fire risks and air quality in the Arctic using these services:

Fire risk:

INFRA

[www.arcticpassion.eu
/wp4/ps4](http://www.arcticpassion.eu/wp4/ps4)

Who is it for?

Arctic citizens,
communities, and local
governmental bodies.

What can you see?

- Ignition risks of vegetation
- Active fires and burnt areas

Use cases

- Sharing information
- Adding field observations

Air quality:

AURORAE

[www.arcticpassion.eu
/wp4/ps5](http://www.arcticpassion.eu/wp4/ps5)

Who is it for?

Arctic citizens, communities, and NGOs.

What can you see?

Current air quality and forecasts.

Use cases

- Monitoring air quality (current and forecasted)
- Sharing information
- Planning mitigation actions

Arctic PASSION's fire risk management and air quality forecast services provide simplified visual access to environmental information from different sources, critical information to support decision-making, community resilience and crisis communication.

This is an illustration of some of the information that can be accessed through INFRA and AURORAE services.

The information illustrated in this example is from July and September 2025.

AURORAE

 air quality measurements

INFRA

 higher wildfire risks

Integrated wildfire and air quality information will substantially advance informed decision-making. Expanding the air pollution monitoring networks and their ability to measure more pollutants is key to improving the coverage of the northernmost Arctic communities.

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